

but at seeing *nails* (gag-àm ; 1. 540). In other words, he seems to have expected a tablet covered with conventional signs which are easily interpreted without any specific spoken language⁵. This may have some importance, since it would seem to imply that the text refers to one of the basic facts about the origin, or invention, of cuneiform, *viz* that the tablet was invented *before* true writing. This can now be easily seen from Schmandt-Besserat's discoveries. It also seems to imply that, according to our poet, purely administrative or economic tablets do not constitute true writing since they do not represent true language (inim!)⁶, which may also be construed as a timely warning to grammarians of Sumerian⁷. Interpreted in this way the line not only confirms and reinforces the main point I tried to make in my earlier contribution ; it also fits in well with, and even completes, the episode known as the « Spell of Nudimmud »⁸ which is placed right at the *beginning* of the series of challenges, solutions and journeys. This episode is undoubtedly about making Sumerian into the international, perhaps universal, language⁹. The episode about writing is a necessary pendant to this in operative systemics, historical reality, and narrative structure (and by that token, poetic intention). And the line saying that tablets preceded true writing thus fits in all points.

The argument proposed here also finds support in the famous line 53 in the Sargon Letter¹⁰. Without much doubt our text has influenced the poet of the Sargon legend, for he adds to the line of technical development of writing, or rather correspondence :

u₄-bi-ta im-ma ḡub-bu ḡé-gál¹ im ḡsi-si¹-ge ba-ra-gál-la-àm

« In those days, writing on tablets certainly existed, but enveloping tablets did not exist ».

So it would seem that our scribes, or poets, of the late 3rd/ early 2nd millennium not only had definite ideas about the sequence tablet → cuneiform writing → letters → envelopes. They also had a clear grasp of the historical¹¹ realities of the development and perhaps even the spread of writing.

1. *Fs. Å.W. Sjöberg*, 1989, 515-24 with earlier literature.

2. Variants disregarded

3. S. Cohen, *Enmerkar and the Lord of Aratta* (Diss.)1973 136.

4. Against Komoróczy, *AoF* 3 (1975) 20 : « Es ist durchaus klar, daß der Dichter des Epos hier die Erfindung der Tontafel (...) ... darstellen wollte. » Somewhat closer and otherwise relevant is his subsequent remark « Ihnen (*scil.* Sumerian *literati*) war sicherlich auch noch bekannt, daß die Schrift in Wirklichkeit *zum Zweck wirtschaftlicher Registrierung* entstanden war, als diese memoriter nicht mehr geführt werden konnte. » (*ibid.* 24 ; my italics). But surely this is in contradiction to the text.

5. Perhaps clearly identifiable drawings – however stylized – of f.i. heads of (kinds of) cattle with strokes for numbers?

6. And there is consequently no need for Komoróczy's ingenious detour via the archaic Uruk tablets (for which see M. Green's marvellous study in *JNES* 39 (1980) 1-35), the more so since it does not explain the difficulty. Still, with M. Green we may now be sure that if the Lord of Aratta ever saw a tablet, it was an Uruk tablet – which he could not read

7. Eg. « Im Sumerischen ist satzlose Sprache möglich. Sie ist vor allem in den Wirtschaftstexten üblich » (A. Falkenstein, *Das Sumerische* (1964) 51).

8. Lines 135-55.

9. See already B. Alster in *RA* 67 (1973) 101-09, and my « Another Attempt at the 'Spell of Nudimmud' » (forthcoming).

10. See J. Cooper & W. Heimpel in *JAOS* 103 (1983) 67-82.

11. Apart from the specific use they make of the absence of envelopes in the story, they could of course hardly pretend that writing did not exist in Sargonic times.

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14) Addenda et corrigenda à P. Attinger, « Éléments de linguistique sumérienne – Au lendemain de la parution de mon ouvrage *Éléments de linguistique sumérienne. La construction de du₁₁/e/di « dire », Orbis Biblicus et Orientalis Sonderband* (Fribourg Suisse/Göttingen 1993), je constate quelques inadvertances et omissions graves dans la *Liste des compositions sumériennes* (pp. 31-59) :

P. 35, *EnkNim* : Ajouter R. Borger, *Or.* 54 (1985) 18-22.

P. 36, *EWO* : La face de CC (*ISSET* 2 60, Ni.9855) contient les ll. 48-50.

P. 47, *LU* texte I : Lire *JNES* 29.

Pp. 50 sq., *Ninšatapada-Rīm-Sîn* : Lettre éditée maintenant par W.W. Hallo *apud* D. Charpin et F. Joannès (éd.), *Marchands, diplomates et empereurs. Etudes sur la civilisation mésopotamienne offertes à Paul Garelli* (Paris 1991), pp. 377-388.

Pp. 56 sq., *SumLet. B : 6* : Un nouveau duplicat est IB 1706, publié par M. Krebernik *apud* B. Hrouda (éd.), *Isin-lšān Bahrīyāt IV (= ABAW NF 105, 1992) pp. 105-107 et pl. 56 (1-fin).*

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